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Interactive Online Modules – Impacting the Individual Learning Success in Engineering Mechanics?

M. Pelz

Technology and Didactics of Technology, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

M. Lang

Technology and Didactics of Technology, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

Y. Özmen

Institute of Mechanics, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

J. Schröder

Institute of Mechanics, University of Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

F. Walker

Didactics of Technology, Technical University of Kaiserslautern
Kaiserslautern, Germany

R. Müller

Chair for Applied Mechanics, Technical University of Kaiserslautern
Kaiserslautern, Germany

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ABSTRACT

The collaborative research project FUNDAMENT (Improvement of individual learning success by the use of digital media in civil engineering) of the University of Duisburg-Essen and the Technical University of Kaiserslautern, which is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), has developed and evaluated so-called interactive online modules (IOM) for the introductory phase of the civil engineering studies (EM), more precise in the courses of engineering mechanics. The IOM consists of learning videos, online exercises and online forums.

These IOM have the objective of increasing the individual learning success of civil engineering students and therefore to minimize the high drop-out rates in engineering sciences in the long term. In this paper the effectiveness of the IOM will be determined on the basis of a longitudinal study in a classic experimental and control group design in the EM 1 course in the first semester. Paper and pencil tests (multiple-choice-single-select test design – multi-matrix) are applied at two measuring points (MP): beginning (MP 1) and end of the first semester (MP 2). Initial analyses of the data are presenting an increase of the mean person ability (dichotomous Rasch model) regarding the achieved scores at both MP. The cause of this increase cannot be defined exactly, an allocation to the IOM is currently not possible due to a small number of participants in the control group.

1 INTRODUCTION

At German universities, an increasing number of first-year students has been recorded in recent years. However, not all of them finish their studies with the intended degree. Records show a high number of student dropouts especially in engineering disciplines for many years. Current studies indicate that 35% of engineering students (relative to the number of first-year students 2012/2013) in Germany finish their studies without a degree [1]. Considering only civil engineering students, a dropout rate of even 42% can be observed [1]. This is not only an issue in Germany, but also a rather common problem in other European countries [i.a. 2,3] and in the United States [4] as well.

According to Heublein et al. [5] dropping out of university in general cannot be reduced to one motive, it is rather a complex and multi-dimensional dropout process that ultimately leads to the students decision to disenroll. The dropout process can be divided into several phases, which are influenced by different factors [5]. In a closer examination of the engineering sciences, performance problems are the main reason for dropping out of university [5]. The performance problems especially emerge in basic subjects like engineering mathematics or engineering mechanics (EM) [6] and are often resulting in failed exams [5]. A possible cause regarding performance problems may be a decrease of special and mathematical knowledge among first-year students [7,8]. In the introductory phase it is extremely difficult for the students to address such knowledge gaps [9]. The importance of the introductory phase is illustrated by the fact, that students without study success in the first semester describe the biggest part of the disenrollment [7].

Heublein & In der Smitten [8] developed a reference model for quality assurance at faculties of engineering sciences to prevent the aforementioned problems. The reference model implies that the use of preventive support measures at different times during the course of the studies may be helpful. The support measures are applied in the preliminary phase (self-assessments and prep courses) as well as in the introductory phase (additional learning offers). At many universities such support measures are already available in different variations, but in most cases only subject-unspecific topics are covered. For instance, engineering application contexts - like those of the EM - remain untreated. Also, only very few prospective or first-year students attend respectively make use of these support measures, further consideration of those who are absent indicate that these are mainly those who urgently need such assistance or offers [5].

2 IOM IN THE INTRODUCTORY PHASE

To oppose the named problematic the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT (Improvement of individual learning success by the use of digital media in civil engineering) was initiated by the University of Duisburg-Essen and the Technical University of Kaiserslautern in 2017. The objective of FUNDAMENT is to support the individual learning processes in civil engineering studies by the use of digital university teaching. A digital support concept was developed based on the previously presented reference model. For this purpose, support measures – focusing on the EM – for the preliminary phase (online self-assessment and online prep course) as well as for the introductory phase (interactive online modules – IOM) were developed.

This paper will only address the introductory phase. Prusty and Russell [10] have already shown in their research – on closer examination of the introductory phase – that first-year students have difficulties in understanding the key core concepts of the EM. A possible reason for this could be the fact that students do not succeed in linking the lecture content with the corresponding key core concepts. Attempts to achieve this connection in physics by additional illustrations of the theoretical facts - e.g. by means of demonstration experiments within the lectures - have no positive effect [11]. No research relating to the EM is available yet.

Individual lecturer-student discourses in tutorials or exercises could achieve an improvement of the conceptual knowledge. Many universities offer such activities, but the need can hardly be met due to increasing numbers of students. At this point the so-called IOM could be helpful. IOM have already been developed in the Anglo-Saxon area, also applied and evaluated, but the individual learning processes are not considered and there are research methodological deficits as well [i.a. 10,12].

Therefore, research on the efficacy of IOM especially in the EM and whether they contribute to the understanding of the corresponding key core concepts is incomplete and needs to be continued. Based on a three pillar concept the IOM have been developed. This concept consists of three digital elements used in the introductory phase specially for the EM 1 and EM 2 courses: learning videos, JACK exercises and anonymous moodle¹ discussion forums.

The first pillar (learning videos) contains two areas of application: On the one hand, the videos provide experiments that were already presented in the lecture in order to illustrate the key core concepts of the EM for self-study or rework. On the other hand, a second category of videos were created: animated slideshows, whose focus is on the teaching and learning support in the area of arithmetic problems. The processing of such exercises requires a conceptual approach and the understanding of basic concepts of the EM. Both types of videos allow students to process the contents of the classroom events regardless of time and place. In this way, a high-quality addition and flexibility to the existing teaching and learning is achieved.

The second pillar of the IOM is described by the implementation of exercises in the server-based system JACK [13], which enables parameterized computer-aided testing with automated feedback generation. The students have the opportunity to work time and location independent on parameterized exercises of different levels of difficulty and receive feedback on the submitted solutions. The feedback function also offers the opportunity to comment on the results. Especially if the results are wrong, hereby the students can be motivated to search for their error in a particular partial result.

¹ <https://moodle.org>, accessed July 11th, 2019.

A stronger involvement of students in the academic community will be supported with online-based communication channels as the third pillar of the IOM. For this moodle forums are used to facilitate communication between students and lecturers, or students among themselves, to clarify content and organizational issues. Mainly in the introductory phase this is a major problem in study programs with large numbers of first-year students and therefore considered a factor for dropping out of university [5].

The created learning videos and JACK-exercises² were developed for the different topics of the EM 1 and EM 2 lectures (EM 1: vector analysis, system of forces, gravity calculation, support, truss, internal force variable, principle of virtual displacements, friction; EM 2: geometrical moment of inertia, tension, bending line, oblique bending, kern, shear force or torsion, stability, composite cross-section, hydromechanics). For the EM 1 lecture four videos and 77 exercises, for the EM 2 lecture seven videos and 60 exercises were developed.

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This paper deals with one of the research questions of the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT: Are the IOM contributing to an increase of the individual learning success of students in the field of the EM in the first semester of the civil engineering studies. In a classic experimental and control group design this research question will be answered longitudinally (Fig. 1). At two measuring points (MP) paper and pencil tests are applied to answer the named research question: beginning of the first semester (MP 1) and end of the first semester (MP 2). In the control group are students who attend the EM 1 course in the conventional concept. In contrast, the experimental group differs by the inclusion of the developed IOM in the EM 1 course. The data were collected in the winter semester 2018/2019. Another paper and pencil test will be used at the end of the second semester (MP 3) to assess the effectiveness of the IOM in the EM 2 events, but this is not part of this paper.

Fig. 1. Longitudinal design of the FUNDAMENT – focussing on the first semester [14]

The results of the applied knowledge tests and the exam grades are used to determine the efficacy of the IOM. The developed test instrument is based on the item pool of the engineering mechanic test (EMT) by Dammann & Lang [15] – technical knowledge, subject-specific modeling ability and mathematical knowledge. It is applied in paper and pencil tests in a multiple-choice-single-select test design (multi-matrix). The EM 1 exam was split in two parts which were written in the middle (EM 1.1) and the end of

² JACK exercises are hereafter abbreviated as JACK.

the first semester (EM 1.2). The usage of the IOM is operationalized by recording the clicks on links that forward to the videos and JACK in the EM 1 moodle environment.

The first MP includes the gathering of demographic variables like gender, final school exam grade, last school grades (math, physics, chemistry, computer science and technology), native language and further information on the educational background.

The structure of the study as a collaborative research project permits conclusions like the generalizability of the results with regard to the effectiveness of the IOM.

4 RESULTS

The results regarding the usage of the IOM presented in this paper originate from the University of Duisburg-Essen. The gathering of the data took place in the winter semester 2018/2019 in the cohort of first-year students of the civil engineering studies. A consent from the students was necessary in order to track the number of clicks on particular parts of the IOM (videos and JACK). Due to the EU data protection directive, this consent form is required for the recording and storage of the relevant data.

A compensation of 20 EUR per student was paid to motivate the students to take part in the paper and pencil tests, in addition, they got bonus points for the second partial exam (EM 1.2) when achieving 50 % of the possible number of points at MP 2. Nevertheless, it has not been possible to persuade a large number of students to participate consistently in the tests. While from the entire cohort 143 students participate in MP 1, only 46 attended the following MP 2. As already mentioned, we can only access corresponding IOM usage data if the consent of the students is on hand. Therefore, the mentioned numbers are reduced to 78 at MP 1 respectively 38 at MP 2. A further reduction occurs in the execution of a longitudinal analysis, then 34 students remain (participation in MP 1, MP 2 and IOM consent).

The remaining students were split into groups in terms of their usage of the IOM. It was differentiated whether the videos and / or JACK were used: This resulted in four user groups: 1. *videos and JACK*, 2. *(only) videos*, 3. *(only) JACK* and 4. *none* (of both). The user group that only used videos is not represented in the collected data, the entire classification can be seen in *Table 1*. Here it can be stated that there is no student who has only used the *videos*, so the group is not listed. Most of the students used both the *videos and JACK*. Remarkable is the small number of students in the group *none*, which is intended as the control group.

Table 1. Classification into IOM user groups

IOM user groups	n	%
videos and JACK	23	70.3
JACK	9	24.3
none	2	5.4
total	34	100.0

The effectiveness of the IOM usage is checked by the achieved person ability in the applied knowledge tests at the beginning (MP 1) and at the end of the first semester (MP 2). The person ability was calculated according to the dichotomous Rasch model. At both MP different test books were used with 68 (MP 1) respectively 59 items (MP 2), which were anchored by 28 items. The tests showed satisfactory reliabilities and

separations for the entire cohort (person reliability = .86, person separation = 2.45, item reliability .94, item separation = 3.93).

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlation between the achieved person ability (MP 1 and MP 2) and the achieved grades in the partial exams (EM 1.1 and EM 1.2). High correlations can be consistently found. A high correlation between the person ability at MP 1 and at MP 2 can be found, as well as regarding both partial exams. There is also a high correlation between the person ability and the partial exams, which leads to the conclusion that the used test instruments are able to reproduce the corresponding knowledge tested in the exams. No correlation between the IOM usage and the person ability respectively the partial exam grades can be found.

Table 2. Correlation (Pearson) between knowledge tests and achieved grades in the part exams

		person ability MP 2	grade EM 1.1	grade EM 1.2
person ability	MP 1	.742**	-.551**	-.567**
	MP 2		-.622**	-.686**
grade	EM 1.1			.627**

** < .01

The descriptive statistics concerning number of clicks on the videos and JACK are shown in Table 3. As well as the achieved person abilities at both MP and the corresponding achieved grades in the partial exams (characteristic 1 - 5 – best: 1). The person ability increases, as well as the part exams are getting better. However, this cannot be attributed solely to the IOM since we cannot make any conclusions in this regard due to the small control group. Thus, statements about the effectiveness of the IOM are not possible at this time.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics regarding IOM clicks (videos and JACK), person ability achieved in the knowledge tests (MP 1 and MP 2 and achieved grades in the part exams (EM 1.1 and EM 1.2)

	n	M	SD	min	max
clicks videos	34	3.26	3.74	0	15
clicks JACK	34	86.50	73.47	0	271
person ability MP 1	34	.05	.60	-.93	1.73
person ability MP 2	34	.73	.76	-.90	2.51
grade EM 1.1	31	3.58	1.25	1.00	5.00
grade EM 1.2	30	2.63	1.52	1.00	5.00

No detailed results can be presented regarding the anonymous moodle forums. The forums were not used at all. In a survey (applied after the second semester) currently under evaluation, the students were asked why they did not use the forums. It has often been stated that they did not know that the forums exist. This is surprising as they were introduced in the lectures as well as the arrangement in the moodle course was chosen that they can be found right at the top. Detailed results of this survey are still pending.

5 SUMMARY

The results evaluated so far in the collaborative research project FUNDAMENT show that students very well accept the IOM (except the anonymous moodle forums). Both the videos and JACK are widely used.

In the considered group of 34 students, an average of 3.26 clicks can be found on the videos, with four videos available. Jack recorded an average of 86.50 clicks at 77 available, with a maximum of 271 clicks, thus an average 3.5 clicks per exercise. After the second semester, the students were given a survey to evaluate the IOM, it is currently being evaluated. One of the questions was related to why the students are not using the anonymous moodle forums. First evaluations show that students did not know that the forums exist. In principle, the forums were pointed out in the lectures and they were positioned prominently in the moodle course. However, it was not clear to the students that they exist, which shows that the IOM have to be advertised more frequently and more actively in the future.

First analysis of the available data show difficulties in the execution of the study. In the longitudinal analysis of the data, it is extremely problematic to get the students to participate in all MP. Already several changes in the execution of the tests brought no long-lasting success. For example, 187 students took part in the test at MP1, but it was only one-third at the subsequent MP at the end of the same semester. In order to evaluate the IOM usage afterwards, the consent of the students is also required. This again reduces the remaining number of students in the study significantly. Subsequently, the control group consists of only two students. Starting points must be found in the future for possible follow-up examinations in order to motivate students to continuously participate in the study. With regard to the pilot phase, changes were already made in the test execution, as the numbers of participants in the pilot phase were even lower. For example, the implementation of the tests was switched from online to paper and pencil. Also, the awarded compensation is now paid after each MP and not as in the pilot phase after the successful completion of the entire study. These changes have led to significantly higher numbers of participants, but the figures at MP 2 are still not satisfactory.

The next steps in FUNDAMENT are the evaluation of the before mentioned survey and the IOM usage in the second semester (MP 3). There will be profound analyses of the data. In order to give generalizable statements regarding the developed digital support concept, the data will be approached both site-specific as well as across both locations.

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